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syllable boundary
- morpheme boundary
= word boundary

Phonology

- Definition of word: = phonological representation of a single basic lexeme
 - o Can be segmented into syllables and conversely each syllable in a sentence is part of a single pword
- Roots usually exist also as independent words, sometimes may not exist independently (usually fossilised derivations or a root having been lost as independent word)
- Segmental properties:
 - o inventory of syllable final C is much smaller in number and with fewer contrasts than that of syllable initial C
 - o syllable final only: p^o, t^o, m^o, n^o, ŋ^o (glottalised allophones), j, h, and nasalized j, h and
 - o /p, t, j, m/ are restricted to final syllables of morphemes, not necessarily word final;
ex.: *gpãn* 'he, polite' < *gp* 'other person' + *ãn* 'that'
 - o when p^o and t^o follow oral vowels, the release of the glottis is accompanied by lowering of the velum
→ glottalisation and nasalization of final stops
 - o voiced and nasalized , occur only intervocalically
 - o nasalized glides occur only in the environment of a nasal vowel in the same syllable
 - o "funny" nasals (= longer duration, less rate of airflow through the nose) only occur in the environment of a following oral vowel or C and only in stressed syllables in complementary distribution with syllable initial plain nasals and syllable final nasals
 - o C-clusters normally only occur within a syllable
 - o Only certain C-clusters can occur across syllable boundaries within the morpheme: /h#C/, /#C/, /N#C(C)/, /m#p(C)/, /n#t(C)/, /ŋ#k(C)/, /ŋl/, /ŋs/, /ms/
ex.: *mamplam* 'mango'
 - o Some clusters almost always occur only in personal names
 - o Across morpheme boundaries these restrictions do not apply
 - o /N#C/ where C is voiced stop can occur in borrowings, but not immediately before the final syllable
 - o Diphthongs never occur in unstressed syllables

- Nasal vowels occur in unstressed syllables if and only if there is an immediately preceding nasal stop
- phonological processes:
 - Where initial C of a penultimate syllable is a nasal stop, and a glide or nasal stop intervenes between the two syllables, then the final vowel is nasal;
 - ex.: *mãw* 'rose'
 - This rule does not hold if there is an intervening morpheme boundary;
 - ex.: *p-n-ãjah* 'exertion' < *-n-+pajah* 'difficult'
 - Nasality as prosody:
 - ♣ Unstressed syllable bears nasal prosody if and only if it begins with a nasal stop
 - ♣ For expressives the nasal prosody can occur on any stressed syllable irrespective of syllable onset, for non-expressives a nasal prosody cannot occur if the syllable onset is /C(h)/ where C is a voiced oral obstruent
 - ♣ If a penultimate syllable is nasalized then the final is also nasalized when its syllable onset can be phonetically nasal (i.e. if the final syllable begins with a glide or a single nasal stop)
 - ♣ The spread of the prosody is in any case blocked by a morpheme boundary
 - ♣ P. 24
 - Frication of /p/:
 - ♣ Domain: word
 - ♣ Only affects initial C of three-syllable words
 - ♣ Sometimes realized as [s] in the environment of following labial
 - ♣ Ex.: *p-mɛn smɛn* 'to amuse, to entertain'
 - Frication of /t/:
 - ♣ Domain: word
 - ♣ /t/ [s] / =_{l / r / n}VC(C)V(C)= ; where the final syllable is not tV(C) ('=' means word boundary)
 - ♣ ex.: *t-n-tt > tntt* and **sntt* 'something burnt'
 - rounding of //:
 - ♣ realized as /u/ in unstressed syllables in the environment of two labial C
 - ♣ within words compulsory, within phrase optional
 - ♣ rounding is optional if vowel in following syllable is // and if it is not the last syllable
 - ♣ ex.: *m-boh > muboh* 'to serve'
 - nasalization:
 - ♣ domain: word

- ♣ when a nasal is infixed before a vowel of a rootmorpheme, this vowel is nasalized
- Diphthong reduction:
 - ♣ Reduced to monophthongs when the word they occur in is cliticised
- h-epenthesis:
 - ♣ domain: phrase
 - ♣ clitics which have no syllable final C add /h/ when they are enclitics and occur last in their phrase
 - ♣ occur not for words which are cliticised, but are not clitics
 - ♣ ex.: 'drœ=nh ka=n='jak
 self 2 IN 2 go
 'You have gone'
- free variations
 - ♣ tendency to drop initial syllables
 - ♣ particularly affects trisyllabic words, especially of structure: C¹C² (C¹= t, c, s / C²= l, n, r) as first syllable
 - ♣ ex.: *snibay* ~ *nibay* 'rice sheaves'
 - ♣ unstressed vowels vary to a great extent
 - ♣
- stress:
 - to distinguish: phrase stress and word stress
 - word stress: on the final syllable
 - phrase stress:
 - ♣ stress is assigned on the level of the phrase
 - ♣ lies on the stressed word of the phrase usually the final or penultimate
 - ♣ ex.: /pa#de/ 'rice'; /m#nã#sah/ 'meeting house'
 - stress is realized when a word is pronounced in its citation form or when it is the stressed word in the phrase
 - an unstressed word in a phrase is termed 'cliticised'
 - words with double stress:
 - ♣ on some words which have a reduplicated structure: (s)^aS-(s)^aS ('s' – unstressed syllable; 'S' – stressed syllable; 'a' – number of the unstressed syllables)
 - ♣ ex.: *ureu'eng-ureu'eng*
 person -person
 'people'
 - ♣ small number which take triple stress

♣ ex.: 'du-'du-khu'eng 'cicada'

- intonation:
 - phrase stress is also important for sentence level intonation patterns
 - peaks and sudden rises in intonation occur on stressed syllables of phrases
 - a core topic NP is marked by a rise or peak in intonation
 - with no core topic some other phrase may bear an intonation peak – this is often the predicate phrase, but after such a predicate phrase there is a much sharper drop in intonation than after a core topic
- syllables:
 - phonological form of final syllable is invariant no morphophonemic rules apply
 - most phonological contrasts are restricted to final syllables – clusters, diphthongs, contrastive nasalization, aspirated, murmured consonants occur only in this syllable
 - many words are monosyllabic, but disyllables are also common
 - most three or four syllable words are either derived from disyllabic or monosyllabic words or are special non-basic vocabulary
 - template: C(C)V(C)
 - in unstressed syllables vowels are considerably shorter and less distinct than in stressed syllables
 - two types of syllable structure:
 - ♣ syllable which can bear stress: C(C)V(C) = S
 - ♣ syllable which never bear stress: CV(C) = s
 - ♣ words that can be stressed: (s)^a S (a ≥ 0)
 - ♣
- clitics:
 - never stressed
 - monosyllables
 - structure like syllables which are never stressed

Morphology and Syntax

- no inflectional morphology Durie: no need to distinguish between gword and lexeme
- no suffixes, only prefixes and infixes
- prefixation:
 - all prefixed morphemes are monosyllables with CV
 - ex.: *pu-blœ* 'to salt'
 - no large number
- Serialisation:
 - Share one or more arguments and this becomes the basis for syntactic “welding” of their two clauses together, so that a compound clause is formed
 - There are various kinds involving different strong welds
 - Strong serialisation: combines two verbs so that they are pronounced

as one phonological phrase

- ♣ Treated syntactically as one predicate with a single set of arguments and adjuncts

- ♣ Agent is only cross-referenced on the first verb

- ♣ Ex.: *gopnyan ban geu=beudöh=êh*

He just 3 rise sleep

'He just got up from sleep'

- Weak serialisation:

- ♣ Does not require the two verbs to be joined as one phonological phrase

- ♣ Pronounced as a single clause without the intonational discontinuity usual between separate clauses

- ♣ Ex.: *awak =nyan ka=ku=poh mate*

Person that IN 1 strike die

'I struck them dead'

- Reduplication:

- All single stressed words can be reduplicated for emphatic effect

- Some words have reduplicated roots

- When a reduplicated word occurs in a stressed position in a phrase, it has a double word stress

- Ex.: *'ma -'ma =mn ji=koh=œk*

Mother mother 1exc 3 cut hair

'Our mother really did get her hair cut'

- Four most instances a word is simply doubled without variation in its form

- Sometimes are phonological variations involved between the two parts lexically conditioned, but certain regular phonological patterns can be discerned:

- ♣ Sometimes only the final syllable of a root is reduplicated

- ♣ Second part may have more syllables: mostly in reciprocal verbal derivatives

- ♣ Stressed syllable may vary: mostly affects the vowel, but also possible the final C and sometimes the preceding C

- ♣ Ex.: *gr'bam-grbum* 'sound of banging about'

- ♣ Occasionally phonological variation in an unstressed syllable

- ♣ Ex.: *ca'lam-ma'lôm* 'irregular'

- Syllable reduplication:

- ♣ Initial syllable in words of three syllables

- ♣ Resulting construction has only a single word stress

- ♣ Ex.: *syesyeda'ra* 'relatives'

- Word combination:

- Juxtaposition of opposites

- Phonological identical with reduplication

- Ex.: *tu'ha-mu'da* 'old and young'

u'roe-ma'lam 'day and night'

- Incorporation: nominals into verbs
 - In post-verbal position, incorporated onto verbal phrase
 - Suffixed nominal is directly attached onto the verb and bears the verbal phrase stress
 - Verb itself is not stressed
 - Indivisible unit
 - Ex.: *ji=jak=siku'la*
3 go school
'He attend school'
 - Distinct from cliticisation of an undergoer argument (here the verb still bears the main stress)
 - Locative Adjunct incorporation:
 - ♣ For certain fixed expressions involving intransitive verbs an adjunct locative NP can be incorporated after the verb
 - ♣ Agent argument cannot intervene
 - ♣ A referential locative adjunct would not be incorporated
 - ♣ Ex.: *gopnyan ka=geu=woe=rumah*
he IN 3 return house
'He has gone home'
 - ka=ji=jak=sikula si=agam=nyan*
IN 3 go school title boy that
'That boy is already going to school'
 - detransitivizing undergoer incorporation:
 - for certain fixed expression involving transitive verbs
 - incorporated element is not referential
 - ex.: *pajoh=bu* 'dine' (lit.: eat rice)
mat=jaroe 'shake hands in greeting' (lit.: hold hands)
 - possessed head of undergoer incorporation
 - after the verb
 - possessor NP can be cross-referenced by pronominal enclitic
 - the possessed head can be interrogated --> preposed before the verb
 - ex.: *gopnyan ka=lôn =têt =ru'moh=geuh*
he IN 1 burn house 3
'I burnt his house'
 - locative undergoer incorporation
 - location assumes the syntactic status of a core role
 - ex.: *ujeuen ka=keunöng bak=lôn*
rain IN struck at I
'The rain came in on me'
- phrase:
 - formed by words which are separated from each other by pause
 - it contains a single stressed word
 - a phrase may also consist of only one word;
ex.: *ureueng = carōng = 'nyan* (' indicates stress)

person clever that
 'that clever person' ('=' means word boundary within a phrase)

- clitics:

- never stressed in any context (Durie's definition of clitics)
- Durie distinguish between cliticised and clitic
- Cliticised = are entities which can be stressed, but are not stressed in this context;
 ex.: *ka = geu = jak = 'woe*
 IN 3 go return
 'he returned'
 geu – clitic
 ka 'already', *jak* 'go' – only cliticised
- Closed set
- Include a variety of parts of speech
- Most commonly occurring as pronouns or prepositions, but there are also clitic verbs, conjunctions and illocutionary markers
- most enclitic pronominals have an epenthetic h when they occur last in their phrase
- proclitic pronominals directly attached to a verb, cross-reference agent arguments
- enclitic pronominals cross-reference non-Agent argument
 - ♣ Undergoer: attached directly to the verb or they may float to the right, attaching to an adjunct phrase
 - ♣ no phrasal discontinuity is pronounced between a verb and a floated clitic
 - ♣ the verb and the adjunct which bears the clitic cannot be stressed separately
 - ♣ ex.: *teungku=jôhan ka=leupah'=geuh u=keude' baroe*
 title Johan IN pass 3 to town yesterday
 'Teungku Johan went off to town yesterday'
 teungku=jôhan ka=leupah u=keude'=geuh
 title Johan IN pass to town 3
 'Teungku Johan has gone to town'
- in a measure phrase the enclitic pronominal can float: occurring separately from the phonological phrase of its head – only possible for core role NP
 - ex.: *li geu=taguen eungkôt*
 much 3 cook fish
 'She cooked a lot of fish'
 - may also float to the right when its head is a core topic: involve a phonological phrase discontinuity with the measure phrase immediately following its head
 - ex.: *boh=u =nyan mandum ka=rhêt*
 fruit coconut that all IN fall
 'Those coconuts have all fallen'
 - may also float into the verbal complex, in between weakly bound elements in a complement verb sequence

- ex.: *awak =jêh ka=mandum=ji=woe*
 person that IN all 3 return
 'Those people have all returned'
- may float past the predicate
- ex.: *boh=u nyan ka=rhêt mandum*
 fruit coconut that IN fall all
 'Those coconuts have all fallen'
- when the head is not the core topic: enclitic pronominals float to the left, around the predicate or to the right
 - ex.: *mandum ka=ji=woe ureueng=nyan*
 all IN 3 return person that
 'Those people have all returned'
- the subject of manner or measure nominal predicate or of a prepositional predicate or of an expression with locative undergoer incorporation:
 clitics are attached to the predicate phrase
 - ex.: *gopnyan lagee= nyan'=geuh*
 he manner that 3
 'He is like that'

- infixation:

- derivational morphology
- insert into the first syllable of a disyllabic word, never final
- infixation only in unstressed syllables
- 2 infixes: *-n-* derives nominals; *-m-* derives verbs – both have prefixing allomorphs
- ex.: *c-n-arrj > cnãrrj* 'cleverness'
- sometimes it is necessary to distinguish between stem and root
 - certain monosyllabic roots form a disyllabic stem
 - ex.: *tt* 'to burn, tr.' > stem: *ttt* > *t-n-tt* 'burning' and *t-m-tt* 'to burn, intr.'
- *-EUM-*
 - infix, but there is also a prefixed allomorph
 - with roots of three or more syllables *-eum-* is prefixed as *meu-*
 - if the verb has a labial initial C the V of the prefix is rounded to *u*
 ex.: *peuranguy* 'to treat' > *mupeuranguy* 'to act'
 - with verb roots beginning with b, a glide, nasal stop or an unaspirated sonorant, *-eum-* is prefixed as *meu-* and if the verb has a labial initial C, the vowel of the prefix is rounded to *u*
 - ex.: *angkôt /angkot/* 'to transport, tr.' > *meuangkôt* 'to transport intr.'
 - *bloe* 'to buy, tr.' > *mubloe* 'to buy, intr.'
 - for all other disyllabic and monosyllabic roots *-eum-* is infixed as *-eum-*
 - infixation is made into the initial syllable of a disyllabic stem
 - an initial p is dissimilated to s
 - for those roots which are already disyllabic, infixation may be made directly

ex.: *pubeuet* 'to teach, tr.' > *seumubeuet* 'to teach, intr.'

- for monosyllabic roots beginning with Cr or Cl form a disyllabic stem by splitting the cluster with an epenthetic *eu* or by reduplication of their initial C (some roots allow both types)
ex.: *plah* 'to split, tr.': two possible stems: *peulah* or *peuplah* > *s-eum-eulah* or *s-eum-uplah* 'to split, intr.'
- other roots with an initial stop form a disyllabic stem by reduplication of their initial C with an epenthetic *eu*
ex.: *jak* 'to go' stem: *jeujak* > *jeu-meu-jak*
poh 'to hit' stem: *peupoh* > *seumupoh* 'to hit, intr.'
- monosyllabic roots beginning with *rh* or *rl* form an irregular disyllabic stem by prefixing *seu* - the reason is that *rh*, *lh* almost always derive from *sr*, *sl*
ex.: *lhap* 'to wipe. tr.' > *seumeulhap* 'to wipe, intr.'
- some roots taking reduplication of an initial *p* with dissimilation to *s* can lose the initial syllable *seu* to give the effect of prefixation
- this is also the case for derivatives or roots beginning with *rh*, *lh* which usually take *-eum-* with the addition of an initial *s*
ex.: *lhöh* 'to dismantle, tr.' > *meulhöh* 'to dismantle, intr.'

○ -EUN-

- infix with a prefixed allomorph
- all roots beginning with a glide, a nasal stop other than *m*, or an unaspirated sonorant, *-eum-* is prefixed as *neu-*
- ex.: *ék /e/* 'to climb, rise' > *neuék* 'rise'
- for monosyllabic roots beginning with *-d*, *-eun-* is prefixed as *neu-*
- infixation into the initial syllables of a disyllabic
 - ♣ *n* of the infix may be denasalised to *l* and a stem initial *t* or labial consonant may be dissimilated to *s*
- infixation directly for disyllabic roots
- for monosyllabic roots: stem is formed to which infix applies:
 - ♣ monosyllabic roots beginning with Cr, Cl, Ch where C is a stop add an epenthetic *eu* or reduplication of their initial C or both
 - ♣ ex.: *bri* 'to give' > *beuneuri* 'gift'
- other roots with an initial stop: reduplication of initial C + epenthetic *eu*
- ex.: *poh*: *peupoh* > *seu-neu-poh* 'hitting'
- monosyllabic roots beginning with *rh* or *rl*: irregular disyllabic stem by prefixing *seu*
- ex.: *lhak* 'to flay' > *seuneulhak* 'tannery'
- some *-eun-* derivatives can drop their initial syllable – most common for stems which have a final syllable identical in form with the underlying monosyllabic root and for derivatives with an initial *s* from a disyllabic root
- ex.: *neucah* 'undergrowth to be cleared' < *ceuneucah*, root *cal* 'to clear'

langgôy 'bun of hair' < *seulanggôy*, root: *sanggôy* 'bun of hair'

- preposition:

- head prepositional phrase
- occur attributively, as predicate, as an adjunct
- prepositions are always unstressed: the following NP bears the phrase stress of the PP
- semantics: a small closed class
-